

A Comprehensive Review on Mechanism of Action of Commonly Used Antidotes in Clinical Toxicology

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Abstract:

Clinical toxicology encompasses the diagnosis, management, and prevention of poisonings caused by exposure to various toxic substances. Antidotes play a crucial role in the treatment of poisoning emergencies, as they counteract the effects of specific toxins and mitigate their harmful effects on the body. Understanding the mechanisms of action of commonly used antidotes is essential for healthcare providers to administer timely and effective treatment. This review provides an overview of the mechanisms of action of several widely utilized antidotes in clinical toxicology such as Naloxone, Atropine, N-acetylcysteine, flumazenil, calcium gluconate, and Digoxin immune FAB. This review highlights on how antidotes are targeting specific toxins or physiological pathways involved in poisoning. The use of antidotes must be guided by a thorough understanding of the toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics of the ingested substance, as well as consideration of individual patient factors such as age, comorbidities, and concurrent medications.

Keywords: Antidote, Naloxone, Calcium gluconate

Introduction:

The International Programme of Chemical Safety broadly defines an antidote as a therapeutic agent that counteracts the toxic actions of a drug/toxin. Broadly, antidotes have been looked at as agents that “modify the kinetics of the toxic substance or interfere with its effect at receptor sites.” This may be as a result of prevention of absorption, binding, and neutralizing the poison directly, antagonizing its end-organ effect, or inhibition of conversion to more toxic metabolites.[1] Here are some common antidotes commonly used in toxicology and their uses.

Digoxin immune FAB:

Digoxin immune fab, also known as digoxin-specific antibody fragments, is a medication used to treat severe digoxin toxicity. Digoxin immune fab (DIF) are mixed anti-digoxin immunoglobulin fragments obtained from healthy sheep immunized with digoxin dicarboxymethoxylamine (DDMA). When administered to the intoxicated patient, DIF binds to digoxin molecules and reduces free digoxin levels. The reduction results in an equilibrium shift away from receptor binding and thereby decreases cardio-toxic effects. The kidney and the reticuloendothelial system eventually clear fab-digoxin complexes. [2]

Octreotide:

Sulfonylurea agents are widely used as therapy for hyperglycaemia in type 2 diabetes mellitus. In overdose, these agents can produce sustained and profound hypoglycemia that is refractory to treatment with dextrose alone. In some cases, management of sulfonylurea overdose with intravenous dextrose leads to hyperglycaemia which promotes insulin release from the pancreas and recurrent hypoglycaemia. Octreotide is a synthetic somatostatin analogue that resembles the native polypeptide in its activity in suppressing levels and activity of growth hormone, insulin, glucagon and

many other gastrointestinal peptides. Mechanism of action of Octreotide in the treatment of in overdose management of sulfonylurea type antidiabetic medications, when recurrent or refractory to parenteral dextrose is through the suppression of insulin secretion. [3]

Dextrose:

Parenteral dextrose is oxidized to carbon dioxide and water, and provides 3.4 cal/g of d-glucose. As an antidote dextrose (antidote) is used for acute alcohol intoxication, sulfonylurea overdose, insulin overdose, hyperkalaemia, and insulin induced hypoglycaemia in paediatric patients. The mechanism of action by which dextrose acts as antidote is that dextrose is source of calories and fluid for patients unable to obtain adequate oral intake, dextrose is the substrate for ATP production for aerobic metabolism and promotes glycogen deposition in the liver. In hyperkalaemia dextrose in combination with insulin stimulates the uptake of potassium by cells (especially in muscle tissue), which in turn lowers serum potassium. [4]

Sodium Bicarbonate:

Sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃) is one of the few pharmacological agents aiming to mimic the endogenous effects of HCO₃⁻. Sodium bicarbonate is widely used in many clinical situations including cardiac arrest and prevention of contrast-induced renal failure and in patients with different types of metabolic acidosis (such as lactic acidosis and diabetic ketoacidosis). Sodium Bicarbonate is a prescription antidote used for reversing Class Ia antiarrhythmics (Quinidine, Procainamide), Class Ib antiarrhythmics (Lidocaine, Phenytoin), Class Ic antiarrhythmics (Propafenone, Flecainide), Class III antiarrhythmics (Amiodarone, Sotalol), Tricyclic antidepressants (Amitriptyline, Doxepin), Antiepileptic medications (Carbamazepine, Lamotrigine, Zonisamide, Lacosamide), Selective

serotonin reuptake inhibitors (Citalopram, Venlafaxine, Fluoxetine), Antihistamines (Diphenhydramine) and Miscellaneous (Cocaine, local anesthetics, Thioridazine, Propranolol, Amantadine, Chloroquine, Hydroxychloroquine, Cyclobenzaprine) and also to treat cardiac arrest. The potential mechanisms of sodium bicarbonate administration include high sodium load, development of metabolic alkalosis with resultant decreased tissue penetration of the toxic substance, and its increased urinary excretion. IV administration of sodium bicarbonate may result in enhanced urinary excretion of certain chemicals such as Metformin through urinary alkalization. Salicylate (aspirin) overdose or poisoning can lead to metabolic acidosis due to its effects on cellular metabolism, sodium bicarbonate can help correct the acid-base imbalance and enhance the elimination of aspirin from the body by alkalinizing the urine. [5]

Flumazenil:

Flumazenil, a specific benzodiazepine antagonist, is useful in reversing the sedation and respiratory depression that often occur when benzodiazepines are administered to patients undergoing anaesthesia or when patients have taken an intentional benzodiazepine overdose. Flumazenil interacts at the central benzodiazepine receptor to antagonize or reverse the behavioural, neurologic, and electrophysiologic effects of benzodiazepine agonists and inverse agonists. It competitively inhibits the activity of benzodiazepine and non-benzodiazepine substances that interact with benzodiazepine receptors site on the GABA/benzodiazepine receptor complex. It can also reverse the binding of benzodiazepines to benzodiazepine receptors. [6]

Naloxone:

Naloxone (N-allylnoroxymorphone) is a pure, competitive opioid antagonist with a high affinity for the mu-opioid receptor, allowing for the reversal of the effects of opioids. It competitively inhibits the sedative, analgesic, and cardiopulmonary depressant effects of opioids at various opioid receptors. Typically, it is used to reverse the sedative and respiratory depressant effects of opioids. It is useful in accidental or intentional overdose and acute or chronic toxicity. Common opioid overdoses treated with naloxone include heroin, fentanyl, carfentanil, hydrocodone, oxycodone, methadone, and others. Naloxone is a highly potent opioid receptor antagonist that is used to reverse the effect of opioid-induced respiratory depression or, when combined with flumazenil, to rule out a pharmacologic cause of unexplained coma.[7]

N-acetylcysteine:

N-acetylcysteine (NAC) is the mainstay of therapy for acetaminophen toxicity. NAC exerts its therapeutic effect in potentially hepatotoxic doses of

acetaminophen through several mechanisms. Paracetamol metabolism in therapeutic dosing primarily occurs through glucuronidation and sulfation(>90%), with less than 5% being oxidized by CYP450 isoform (predominately CYP2E1) to produce a toxic metabolite called N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone imine (NAPQI), which is the precursor to cellular injury. Glutathione in the liver can normally detoxify these minuscule quantities of NAPQI and prevent tissue damage. In potentially hepatotoxic acetaminophen overdose, glucuronidation and sulfation pathways are saturated, and the CYP450 pathway takes more significance, producing more toxic metabolites that deplete the glutathione reserves, leading to their accumulation and hence tissue injury by binding to cellular macromolecules. NAC repletes glutathione reserves by providing cysteine, which is an essential precursor in glutathione production. NAC by itself also binds to the toxic metabolites and scavenges free radicals. It also increases oxygen delivery to tissues, increases mitochondrial ATP production, and alters the microvascular tone to increase the blood flow and oxygen delivery to the liver and other vital organs. [8]

Protamine sulfate:

Protamine sulfate is a polycationic, highly positively charged protein derived from salmon sperm protein. The anticoagulant activity of heparin results from its binding to the serine protease inhibitor, antithrombin III (ATIII). Heparin binding causes a conformational change in ATIII that results in enhanced inhibition of thrombin and other serine proteases involved in the blood clotting cascade. Protamine has been used to neutralize anticoagulation due to unfractionated heparin administration (UFH) after cardiac bypass surgery or any other cardiovascular surgical procedures. The mechanism of action of protamine in heparin overdose involves binding to the negatively charged heparin molecules, forming a stable complex, and displacing ATIII from the heparin:ATIII complex, thereby effectively blocking anticoagulation effect of Heparin. [9,10]

Calcium gluconate:

Calcium gluconate is a medication used to manage hypocalcaemia, cardiac arrest, and cardiotoxicity due to hyperkalaemia or hypermagnesaemia. Calcium gluconate has also been used in the management of β -blocker toxicity, calcium-channel blocker toxicity, magnesium toxicity, and hydrofluoric acid burns. In treating hydrofluoric acid burns, calcium is a mainstay of treatment that functions by binding to fluoride ions, effectively neutralizing them to prevent further toxicity. Furthermore, fluoride can cause hypocalcemia, possibly due to the formation of fluorapatite salt, thus decreasing free calcium levels within the serum. Calcium gluconate directly

replenishes ionized calcium levels within the blood in cases of fluoride-induced hypocalcaemia. Calcium may be useful in beta-blocker overdose in patients with shock refractory to other measures. The calcium effect in beta-blocker toxicity appears to be due to the role of calcium in increasing cardiac inotropy as the influx of calcium into the cardiac cell contributes to the contraction of myofibrils. Calcium gluconate also plays a role in the treatment of calcium-channel blocker toxicity. calcium-channel blocker toxicity causes hypotension, bradycardia, and a decrease in cardiac contractility. The reasoning behind calcium's mechanism against calcium-channel blocker toxicity is to overwhelm the calcium receptors to antagonize the calcium-channel blocker competitively. Thus, restoring cardiac contractility, which, along with IV fluids, can ameliorate the hypotensive symptoms of calcium-channel blocker toxicity. [11]

Deferoxamine:

Deferoxamine is a medication used for iron (approved indication) and aluminium toxicity (off-label). Deferoxamine is a molecule produced by the fermentation of *Streptomyces pilosus*. It binds free plasma iron and excess iron within cells. Deferoxamine chelates iron by forming a stable complex that prevents the iron from entering into further chemical reactions. Deferoxamine chelates non-transferrin bound iron (free iron), iron in transit between transferrin and ferritin (labile chelating iron pool), hemosiderin, and ferritin. Although deferoxamine can directly bind and remove iron from myocardial cells, it will not bind iron already bound to molecules such as transferrin, haemoglobin, or cytochrome. When bound, the resultant ferrioxamine is very water-soluble. If chelation occurs in hepatocytes, the compound will be excreted in bile, and when chelation occurs with free iron in plasma or other tissues, it is excreted by the kidneys. Deferoxamine can also bind aluminium within the plasma to form aluminioxane, which is renally excreted. In the case of chronic kidney disease progresses to end-stage renal disease patients, the product is dialyzable using a high-flux membrane. Deferoxamine can draw aluminium deposited in tissues into the plasma. [12]

Atropine:

Atropine or atropine sulfate carries FDA indications for anti-sialagogue/anti-vagal effect, organophosphate/muscarinic poisoning, and bradycardia. Atropine acts as a competitive, reversible antagonist of muscarinic receptors: an anticholinergic drug. Acetylcholine works on three different receptors that merit attention in nerve agent poisonings. Atropine is only useful to counter muscarinic effects (pralidoxime and benzodiazepines act on the others). Atropine is an antimuscarinic that works through competitive inhibition of postganglionic acetylcholine receptors

and direct vagolytic action, which leads to parasympathetic inhibition of the acetylcholine receptors in smooth muscle. The end effect of increased parasympathetic inhibition allows for preexisting sympathetic stimulation to predominate, creating increased cardiac output and other associated antimuscarinic adverse effects. Atropine, used in organophosphorus poisoning, is an example of an antidote that is used to counter and mitigate the several muscarinic effect of the poison. [13]

Conclusion:

These are just a few examples of antidotes, and their use depends on the specific toxin or medication involved in the poisoning. In many cases, antidotes are used in conjunction with supportive care and medical interventions tailored to the individual patient's condition.

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